

A Short Note on Structure of Turbulent Boundary Layer

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ABSTRACT

A close examination of the turbulent boundary layer data reveals that the velocity profile exhibits two different types of similarity in the inner and outer regions, with the boundary layer being divided into region 1 (the inner region/wall region), where the flow is described by the law of the wall, and region 2 (the outer region/wake region), where the flow is governed by the law of the wake. Experimental data with different pressure gradients—zero pressure gradient (ZPG), adverse pressure gradient (APG), and favourable pressure gradient (FPG)—demonstrate that the wall region remains unaffected by external manipulation, while the outer region accounts for the effects of external manipulation. It is shown that as the Reynolds number increases, inner region becomes a smaller fraction of the total boundary layer. Additionally, it is shown that the locus of the endpoint of the boundary layer for ZPG flow can be utilized for identification of pressure gradient of any flow.

KEYWORDS: *Turbulent Boundary Layer, Inner Region, Outer Region, Law of the Wall, Law of the Wake, Pressure Gradient, Reynolds number.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The turbulent boundary layer is a complex and fundamental phenomenon in fluid dynamics, characterized by chaotic fluid motion near solid boundaries. Understanding its behaviour is crucial for a wide range of applications, from aerospace engineering to environmental flow modelling. In turbulent boundary layers, velocity gradients, pressure fluctuations, and vortical structures interact in ways that significantly affect drag, heat transfer, and momentum transport. Despite extensive research, many aspects of turbulence near walls remain challenging to model and predict.

This paper explores the key features of turbulent boundary layers, including their structure and scaling laws, focusing on their key characteristics.

The experiments used in this analysis were conducted by Österlund (1999) on zero pressure gradient (ZPG) flow, by Jones (1998) on favourable pressure gradient (FPG) flow, and by Marusic and Perry (1995) on adverse pressure gradient (APG) flow. These studies have been widely shared with the scientific community through published papers.

2. STRUCTURE OF BOUNDARY LAYER: EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE

The three velocity profiles from the ZPG flow dataset (Österlund, 1999) are shown in Figure 1 (a), where velocity (u) in meters per second (m/s) is plotted against the y -coordinate (in meters), representing the distance from the wall of a flat plate. The data reveal that it is difficult to describe the flow with a single equation.

As seen in Figure 1(a), the velocity profile exhibits a horizontal tangent at the outer edge of the boundary layer, where velocity, $u = U_o$.

Figure1. ZPG flow velocity profiles: (a) in (u, y) coordinate, (b) in $(u/U_o, y/y_o)$ coordinate.

It is also evident that the value of $y = \delta$ at the outer edge of the boundary layer cannot be fixed due to asymptotic behaviour of the curve. The value of $u = U_o$ represents, however, the position of the asymptote at the outer edge of the boundary layer and is more easily determined. Considering the asymptotic behaviour at the outer edge of the boundary layer, one arrives at the following definition:

$$y \rightarrow \delta = y_o, u \rightarrow U_o$$

The same data is presented in non-dimensional form, i.e., u/U_o and y/y_o , in Figure 1(b). This plot reveals that the velocity profiles, when scaled this way, are not self-similar.

Prandtl (1933) concluded that the time mean velocity, u near the smooth wall must depend upon the density ρ and viscosity μ of the fluid, the shear stress at the wall τ_w and on the distance from the wall, y . Thus, near the smooth wall, there is a functional relationship:

$$u = u(\rho, \mu, \tau_w, y) \quad (1)$$

From dimensional analysis the functional relationship can be written in the form:

$$u/v_* = f(yv_*/\nu) \quad (2)$$

where shear velocity, $v_*^2 = \tau_w/\rho$ and kinematic viscosity, $\nu = \mu/\rho$. Introducing $u^+ = u/v_*$ and $y^+ = yv_*/\nu$ equation (2) can be written as:

$$u^+ = f(y^+) \quad (3)$$

Velocity profiles of three different pressure gradients, i.e., ZPG, APG & FPG are presented in Figure 2 where u^+ is plotted as a function of y^+ .

Figure 2. Velocity, u^+ as a function of y^+ .

Figure 2 shows that the velocity profiles for ZPG, APG, and FPG flows coincide up to a certain distance y^+ from the wall, which can be described by a single formulation. This supports the idea that the u^+, y^+ variables effectively characterize the boundary layer and that the law of the wall is universal, unaffected by pressure gradients.

3. LAW OF THE WALL AND LAW OF THE WAKE

Very close to the wall, experimental data can be described by the linear relationship $u^+ = y^+$ (see Figure3). This region is viscous sub-layer where viscous stress predominates.

Prandtl (1933) proposed a logarithmic form of the law of the wall for variation of velocity in the so-called overlap region at large distance from the wall

$$u^+ = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln y^+ + B \tag{4}$$

Where κ is the von Karman constant and B is the constant of integration. Values of κ and B , as proposed by different researchers, are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of κ & B proposed by different researchers

Author	κ	B	Flow
Coles (1956)	0.4	5.1	Boundary Layer
Laufer (1954)	0.334	5.5	Boundary Layer
Österlund (1999)	0.384	4.08	Boundary Layer
Nezu & Rodi (1986)	0.412	5.29	Open Channel
McKeon et al. (2004)	0.421	5.6	Pipe

The region described by the logarithmic law is called the logarithmic region/overlap region where both, viscous and turbulent stresses are present. The region starting from the wall to the end of the overlap region is called wall region. The extent of the wall region depends on Reynolds number. Both laws, linear and logarithmic, do not actually capture the data points in the buffer region (marked in Figure 3).

Beyond the overlap region, there is outer layer where influence of wall is practically absent, and turbulent stress predominates. Figure 3 shows that experimental data in the outer region deviate from the log law. This deviation resembles a wake when viewed from the free stream. A similar wake can be found in channel and pipe flow and in the turbulent boundary layer but in varying amount.

Logarithmic law is too simple for describing the wake region. Accordingly, based on the idea of Coles (1956), the law of the wall should be replaced by:

$$u^+ = f(y^+) + A(x)w(\eta) \quad (5)$$

where $A(x)$ is the amplitude function, $w(\eta)$ is the wake function and $\eta = y^+ / y_o^+$, $y_o^+ = y_o v_* / \nu$ being the boundary layer thickness. The wake function is defined as the difference between the measured data in the outer region and the extension of the logarithmic law in this region. Coles proposed $A(x) = \Pi(x) / \kappa$, where $\Pi(x)$ is wake/profile parameter which is dependent on the streamwise distance, x , for pressure gradient flow while independent of stream wise distant for ZPG flow on a flat plate, i.e., for ZPG flow $\Pi(x) = \Pi$. Hinze (1975) proposed an empirical equation for wake function:

$$w(\eta) = 2 \sin^2(\pi\eta / 2) \quad (6)$$

Using the above empirical equation, Coles' law of the wake law takes the form:

$$u^+ = (1/\kappa) \ln y^+ + B + (2\Pi(x)/\kappa) \sin^2(\pi\eta / 2) \quad (7)$$

The above law of the wake is shown in Figure 3 also.

Figure 3. Linear law, logarithmic law, and law of the wake compared with the ZPG data.

It can be understood that the logarithmic law applies only in the overlap region, while the log-wake law is applicable to the entire boundary layer, excluding the viscous sublayer. The main criticisms of these laws are: (i) they do not satisfy the no-slip condition at the wall, and (ii) they fail to meet the requirement for a non-zero velocity gradient at the outer edge of the boundary layer. Since the log-wake law is a composite model, it is challenging to determine the exact transition from the inner region to the wake or outer region.

Objection (i) can be resolved by using Spalding's (1961) law of the wall, which has the following form:

$$y^+ = u^+ + A \left[\exp(\kappa u^+) - 1 - \kappa u^+ - (\kappa u^+)^2 / 2 - (\kappa u^+)^3 / 6 - (\kappa u^+)^4 / 24 \right] \quad (8)$$

The above formulation has the advantage of being applicable right from the wall. However, Spalding's attempt to extend the expression to the entire boundary layer by selecting constants $\kappa = 0.4$ and $A = 0.1108$ was too ambitious. Figure 4(a) shows how the above relation traces the data points.

Figure4. Demonstration of how the law aligns with the ZPG data: (a) Spalding’ law (1961), (b) modified Spalding’ law.

Persen (1976) thoroughly examined the applicability of Spalding’s formulation (8) against the voluminous data presented at the Stanford Conference (1968) on turbulent boundary layer [ref. Coles and Hirst (1968)] and found the appropriate values of κ and A , respectively as

$$\kappa = 0.53227 \text{ and } A = 0.015 \tag{9}$$

which makes the Spalding’s formulation valid in the region near the wall. Spalding’s law with modified constants (as in Eq.9) is shown in Figure 4(b).

Persen (1976) proposed a formulation for the wake function to represent the data points in the outer region, accounting for any external influences or manipulations.

Persen (1976) proposed the following expression for the wake law:

$$(u^+ - u_{\infty}^+) / (\xi - u_{\infty}^+) = \exp[-(y_o^+ - y^+) / \alpha^2] \tag{10}$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u &\rightarrow U_o \text{ as } y \rightarrow \delta \\ u^+ &\rightarrow U_o / \nu_* = \xi \text{ as } y^+ \rightarrow \delta \nu_* / \nu = y_o^+ \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{11}$$

u_{∞}^+ = curve fitting constant,

$$(1/\alpha^2) = \left[\ln(\xi - u_{\infty}^+) - \ln(u_1^+ - u_{\infty}^+) / (y_o^+ - y_1^+) \right]^2 \tag{12}$$

Here (u_1^+, y_1^+) is the point where the law of the wall meets with the law of the wake. The boundary layer ends at $y^+ = y_o^+$ for which $u^+ = \xi$. It should be noted that the Persen’s wake law has a clear advantage, as it demonstrates a horizontal tangent at the outer edge of the boundary layer.

Modified Spalding’s law and Persen’s wake law (1976) are compared with ZPG, APG and FPG data in Figure 5.

Figure 5. ZPG ($Re_\theta = 2654$), APG ($Re_\theta = 10997$), and FPG ($Re_\theta = 1615$) data fitted to the modified Spalding’s law of the wall and Persen’s wake law (1976). APG and FPG data are shifted by +5 units and -5 units respectively.

4. EXTENT OF THE WALL REGION

Extent of wall region (or inner region) can be expressed by the ratio y_1^+ / y_o^+ . This ratio is determined for all flows and presented in Figure6 as a function of Re_θ . In essence, y_1^+ / y_o^+ is a measure of the non-dimensional quantity y / δ from the wall below which law of the wall governs the flow and above which law of the wake takes over.

Physically, the results suggest that as the momentum thickness Reynolds number increases, the wall region represents a smaller portion of the total boundary layer.

Figure6. Extent of the inner region as a function of Reynolds number.

4.1 LOCUS OF ξ

The locus of ξ defines a curve that marks the endpoint of the boundary layer. For ZPG, APG and FPG flow, the curves are shown in Figure 7 (a). This curve changes with external manipulation, while for ZPG case can be explicitly represented by the following expression:

$$y_o^+ = 0.216 \exp(0.35259\xi) \quad (13)$$

The Figure 7(a) shows that an adverse pressure gradient pushes the profile upward from the ZPG flow, while a favourable pressure gradient pushes the profile downward from the ZPG flow. Therefore, the loci of ξ for ZPG flow (Eq. 13) have great significance, as they can help identify the pressure gradient within a flow.

Figure7. Locus of ξ : (a) ZPG, APG and FPG data from Österlund (1999), Marusic and Perry (1995) and Jones (1998) respectively, (b) ZPG data from Österlund (1999) compared with Perry (1966) and Newman (1951), Bolm (1970) and McKeon et al. (2004).

The above statement is further validated using other sets of data points, including APG flow from Perry (1966), and Newman (1951), FPG flow from Bolm (1970) as referenced in Persen (1978), and pipe flow data from McKeon et al. (2004), as shown in Figure 7(b).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The turbulent boundary layer can be explained using the modified Spalding's law for the inner region, which follows the no-slip condition, and Persen's wake law for the outer region, which satisfies the zero velocity gradient at the outer edge. Experimental evidence indicates that the inner region is self-similar and unaffected by external influences, while the outer region accounts for the effects of external manipulation.

Experimental evidence suggests that at extremely high Reynolds numbers, the wall region becomes negligible in comparison to the entire boundary layer.

The locus of ξ for zero pressure gradients (ZPG) flow can be used to identify the pressure gradient: if the coordinate of the boundary layer's endpoint lies above the locus of ξ for ZPG flow, it indicates an adverse pressure gradient (APG) flow, while if it lies below; it indicates a favourable pressure gradient (FPG) flow.

REFERENCES

- [1] Österlund, J. M. (1999). Experimental Studies of Zero Pressure-Gradient Turbulent Boundary-Layer Flow. PhD Thesis, Department of Mechanics, Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm.

- [2] Jones, M. B. (1998). Evolution and Structure of Sink-Flow Turbulent Boundary Layers. PhD Thesis, University of Melbourne, Australia.
- [3] Marušić, I., and Perry, A. E. (1995). A Wall-Wake Model for the Turbulence Structure of Boundary Layers, Part 2. Further Experimental Support. *J. of Fluid Mech.*, 298, pp. 389-407.
- [4] Prandtl, L. (1933). Neuereergebnisse Der Turbulenzforschung. – *Z. VDI*. 77, Nr. 5, pp.105-114.
- [5] Coles, D.E. (1956). The Law of the Wake in the Turbulent Boundary Layer, *J. Fluid Mech.*1,pp. 191-226.
- [6] Hinze J. O. (1975). *Turbulence*, McGraw-Hill, NewYork.
- [7] Laufer, J. (1954). Investigation of Turbulent Flow in a Two-Dimensional Channel, Report 1053, 1247-1266.
- [8] Nezu and Rodi. (1986). Open-Channel Flow Measurements with a Laser Doppler Anemometer, *J. of Hyd. Engg*, Vol.112, No.5.
- [9] McKeon et al. (2004). Further Observations on the Mean Velocity Distribution in Fully Developed Pipe Flow”, *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 501, pp. 135-147.
- [10] Spalding, D. B. (1961). A Single Formula for the Law of the Wall, *J. of Applied Mechanics*, Vol.28, Ser.E. pp. 455-458.
- [11] Persen, L. N. (1976). An Examination of the Law of the Wake in a Turbulent Boundary Layer. Proc. from the Theodorsen Colloquium, Universitetsforlaget, 1976.
- [12] Coles, D. E. and Hirst, E. A. (1968). Computation of Turbulent Boundary Layers, AFSOR-IFP- Stanford Conference, Vols. 1 and 2.
- [13] Persen, L. N. (1978). Turbulent Boundary Layers, Technical report No. 78:1, Institutt for Mekanikk, NTh, Universitetet I Trondheim, Norway.